

Ph 69

UDC 537.311.33:546.23

ACTA POLYTECHNICA SCANDINAVICA

PHYSICS INCLUDING NUCLEONICS SERIES No. 69

Non-ohmic Effects in Hexagonal Selenium Single Crystals

SIMO O. HEMILÄ

Technical University, Otaniemi-Helsinki

*THESIS FOR THE DEGREE OF DOCTOR OF TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTED BY THE TECHNICAL
UNIVERSITY, OTANIEMI-HELSINKI.*

HELSINKI 1969

P R E F A C E

This work was carried out during the years 1968 and 1969 in the Technical University of Helsinki, Otaniemi. I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Professor ERKKI LAURILA, member of the Academy of Finland, for valuable discussions and his encouragement in the course of the work.

I am indebted to Professor TOR STUBB and his research group for their interest in this work. Fruitful discussions with Dr. TURKKA TUOMI are also gratefully acknowledged. Mr. MATTI SUOMINEN and Mr. JOEL SELIGSON carried out part of the measurements with the financial support of The Finnish Research Council for Technical Sciences.

The selenium crystals Se1, Se2, Se3, and Se7 were provided by Prof. T. STUBB and the crystals Se4, Se5, and Se6 by Dr. J. E. HARRISON.

Helsinki, September 1969

Simo Hemilä

CONTENTS

	Page
Preface	3
1. Introduction	7
2. Experimental	11
2.1. Crystals and apparatus	11
2.2. Steady state conductivity	12
2.3. Transients	13
2.4. Quenching of photoconductivity	16
2.5. Conductivity at 80°K in the dark	20
2.6. Other low field measurements	22
2.7. High field pulse experiments	23
3. Interpretation of the results	25
3.1. Origin of the non-ohmic effects in selenium	25
3.2. Barrier model of photoconductivity in Se	26
3.3. Non-ohmic effects according to the dislocation recombination model ..	28
4. Discussion	36
Summary	40
References	41

1. INTRODUCTION

Non-ohmic effects are changes in the electric conductivity of a material produced by a change in the electric field. These effects have been observed in almost every semiconductor as there are many mechanisms for non-ohmic behavior. If a distinction between different types of effects were possible, valuable information might be gained about the properties of the material studied.

Several types of non-ohmic effects in hexagonal Se single crystals have been reported in the literature. Detailed studies of the resistance of single crystals as a function of electric field have been carried out by H e n k e l s [1] and by P l e s s n e r [2]. Non-ohmic effects appeared at very low fields, a few V/cm. When increasing the electric field the steady state conductance increased, except in the case of high temperature and low electric field, when the conductance decreased with increasing field. Slow transients in the conductance were observed after the change of electric field. Both authors stated that these phenomena could not be caused by any contact effect, and suggested potential barriers to explain the results.

More recently, determinations of the steady state current as a function of voltage have been carried out by P o l k e, S t u k e, and W i n a r i c k y [3], by B a k i r o v and D z h a l i l o v [4], and by G r a e f f e and H e l e s k i v i [5]. At liq. nitrogen temperature characteristics $I \propto U^n$ have been observed with n between 2 and 3, while at room temperature the conductance was constant at small voltages but started to increase at higher fields. In these works the non-ohmic current was stated to be space charge limited. However, the ordinary SCLC of homogeneous crystal can not explain these results, as the dependence of the current on the crystal thickness, the potential distribution along the crystal, and the order of magnitude of the current did not agree with the theory of SCLC in a homogeneous crystal [5].

S t u k e has determined current vs. temperature dependences in Se using various electric fields [6]. At room temperature and above the conductivity did not depend on electric field and followed an exponential temperature dependence

$$\sigma = \sigma_1 e^{-E_B/kT}, \quad (1)$$

where σ_1 and E_B are constants. Thus, $\log \sigma$ vs. $1/T$ was a straight line with slope $-E_B$. At lower temperatures there was a transition to second linear region with smaller E_B , and this »low temperature E_B » depended strongly on the electric field, decreasing with increasing voltage. This means, that the exponent n in the characteristic $I \propto U^n$ increases steadily from unity as the temperature decreases.

Slow conductance transients have been described in several works [1, 2, 5, 7]. Typical transients are similar to those presented in Fig. 2 later in this work, but transients have varied strongly depending on temperature, on electric field range used, on the treatment of the crystal etc.

G o b r e c h t and H a m i s c h have studied effects of high electric field pulses on the conductivity of selenium [8]. The range of the fields used was from 5 to 40 kV/cm. Transients similar to those observed at lower fields and the increase of steady state conductance with field were the main effects of the pulses. These effects increased with the absolute magnitude of high field, but occurred similarly when either a transverse a.c. pulse or longitudinal d.c. pulse was used. High field pulses quenched the low field photoconductivity both at room temperature and at 80 °K when applied during the decay of photoconductivity. Gobrecht and Hamisch explained their results by assuming that field is able to excite current carriers from the traps to the allowed band in a homogeneous crystal. F u h s and S t u k e have also observed the quenching of photoconductivity when pulses of 2 to 10 kV/cm were applied during the decay of photoconductivity [9].

The mobility mechanism of holes in hexagonal selenium single crystals is controversial. A mechanism of barrier limited mobility have been proposed by several workers [1, 2, 6, 7, 10]. Stuke suggested, that these barriers are small angle boundaries [6] and Tuomi assumed these boundaries in his photoconductivity model [10]. According to this model the barrier consists of parallel positively charged dislocations in the small angle boundary. To compensate the positive charge of dislocations free holes are removed from the layer around the boundary. The conductance of these layers (and hence of the crystal) is determined by the very small density of free holes left in the space charge regions. A wide range of experimental results have been interpreted according to this concept:

a) Thermoelectric power and Hall voltage results, interpreted according to the conventional equations, give a hole density in selenium of the order of 10^{14} to 10^{15} cm^{-3} which does not vary much with temperature or illumination [1, 2, 6, 10, 11, 29]. On the other hand, d.c. conductivity increases exponentially with temperature according to Eq. 1. Therefore, the d.c. mobility of holes increases exponentially with temperature and also increases strongly with illumination. According to the barrier model the density of free holes in barrier regions increases exponentially with temperature, and illumination decreases the height of the barriers.

b) Photoconductivity and thermally stimulated conductivity data can not be interpreted according to ordinary models of homogeneous photoconductors [7, 9, 10]. In the interpretation of PC results T u o m i assumes dislocation recombination [10] and F u h s and S t u k e hopping recombination [9], both assume hole depletion layers.

c) Electric properties of Se crystals are strongly changed by deformation and heat treatment. The observed effects are in agreement with the idea of barrier limited mobility [6].

On the other hand information about the microscopic mobility of holes in Se has been provided by several types of studies carried out during recent years. Table I gives a rough summary of the results of these measurements.

T a b l e 1. Microscopic mobility of holes in selenium along the hexagonal *c*-axis

Method	Ref.	Representative values in cm^2/Vs	Remarks
Phonon drag	12,13	200°K: ca. 75, ca. 8	Ref. 13: illumin. necessary Ref. 12: also in dark
Acoustoelectric current saturation	14	300°K: 26 80°K: 30	Illumination necessary at low temperature
Magnetoresistance	15	270°K: ca. 20 83°K: ca. 80	Illumination does not have much effect
High frequency conductivity	16,11	300°K: 30 ... 300 80°K: 240 ... 2400	Hole density $10^{14} \dots 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ have been assumed here (TEP- and Hall-measurements)
Transient photoconductivity	17	300°K: $\approx$ 32 80°K: ca. 60	Photoconductivity mobility was $40 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ at 300°K
Infrared reflection bands	18	300°K: ca. 20	

According to these results the microscopic hole mobility parallel to the *c*-axis is about $20 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ at room temperature and increases slightly with decreasing temperature. The room temperature value is two to three decades larger than the macroscopic d.c. mobility. Even so, it is a small value. Assuming an effective mass of holes equal to the free electron mass and a hole thermal velocity of 10^7 cm/s one obtains a mean free path at room temperature of about $13 \text{ \AA}$, or a few lattice constants. Therefore the concept of deformation potential scattering is rather far stretched in the case of selenium. Unfortunately the mobility mechanisms of crystals with small mobilities can not so easily be used in the interpretation of results like those of Table 1.

According to the barrier model concept, it is possible to study the microscopic mobility of holes by experiments insensitive to barriers. However, definite difficulties

arise when one tries to interpret results like those of the acoustoelectric effect [14] according to the small angle boundary barrier concept. Thus the picture of the conductivity mechanism in Se is still ambiguous and more information is needed.

In this work the non-ohmic effects of various types of Se single crystals were studied systematically at different temperatures. The aims of the work were to determine the common phenomena in different types of crystals, to make an unified interpretation of these effects, and to obtain information about the mobility mechanism in hexagonal Se single crystals.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Crystals and apparatus

Many properties of hexagonal Se are quantitatively quite similar in different types of single crystals, e.g. the temperature dependence of dark conductivity (Eq. 1). On the other hand, some properties vary strongly from crystal to crystal. For example, the photoconductivity in the temperature range 80 °K to 300 °K increases with temperature in some Se crystals but decreases in others [10, 19, 20]. To distinguish the effects of crystal imperfections, several crystals were used in this work, the basic information on which is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Selenium single crystal specimens

Crystal code	Length in mm	Cross section area in mm ²	Low field dark conductivity at 300 °K $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}^*$	Method of growing	Growing Ref.
Se1	2	0.7	10	Slowly from the melt	21,22
Se2	5.5	0.16	6	From the gas phase	23
Se3	5	4	8	Traveling solvent method, ca. 100 ppm TI	24
Se4	5	2	3	From the melt in pressure	25
Se5	12	1.5	1.5	»	25
Se6	5	25	4	»	25
Se7	6	2	-	Slowly from the melt, 160 ppm Cl	(22)

* S = Siemens = mho, $\mu\text{S} = 10^{-6}$ mho

Electroplated nickel contacts were used except in crystals Se3 and Se6 which were provided with evaporated gold contacts. In all crystals the electric field was in the direction of *c*-axis. Point contact voltage probes were used in crystals Se3, Se4, and Se5 when studying the quality of the contacts. Measurements were carried out partly at room temperature, and partly at about liq. nitrogen temperature (values 300 °K and 80 °K are used for these temperatures in this work). In addition, some series of measurements were carried out while varying the temperature. The circuit for these d.c. electric field measurements is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Equipment for non-ohmic studies at low electric fields.

The fast change of either the direction or the magnitude of the voltage was possible by manually switching between two regulated voltage sources.

Some pulse measurements were performed in crystal Se6 to obtain information of non-ohmic effects at higher fields. Single pulses with amplitude 800 to 4000 V and duration 50 to 200 μ s were obtained from a regulated high voltage source by using spark gap switches. The voltage across and the current through the crystal were recorded during the pulse by oscilloscope photographs.

2.2. Steady state conductivity

The steady state current vs voltage characteristics of a specimen can be described by a logarithmic derivative $n = d \log I / d \log U$. This is a slope of current vs voltage curve on log-log-paper, or an exponent in the expression $I \propto U^n$ in a limited voltage range. In the ohmic voltage region n is one.

At temperatures above 0 °C n was close to unity in every selenium crystal studied, both in darkness and when illuminated. The corresponding low field conductivity values at 300 °K are presented in Table 2. Small deviations from the value $n = 1$ were observed. Often n was somewhat larger than one (1,05 ... 1,2) but values smaller than one were also observed in some circumstances, especially at higher temperatures or when illuminated.

When illuminated at 80 °K n was somewhat larger than one, 1,05 to 1,2, even at small voltages. In crystals Se6 and Se7 this low temperature measurement was extended to higher fields. In both crystals n started to decrease at a field of the order 500 V/cm reaching values well below one. Similar saturation effect in the illuminated crystal at low temperature have been reported in Ref. 3. The results at 80 °K in darkness will be discussed in Ch. 2.5.

The temperature dependence of dark conductivity in crystals Se1 to Se4 were checked in the room temperature region. In all these crystals the conductivity was proportional to a factor $\exp(-E_B/kT)$, where the value of E_B was about 0.14 eV in crystals Se1, Se3, and Se4, but 0.2 eV in crystal Se 2.

2.3. Transients

Typically, an increase of voltage caused an instantaneous increase of conductivity and then a slow decreasing transient, while a decrease of voltage caused a sudden conductance drop followed by a slow increasing transient (Fig. 2.). The instantaneous change in conductivity when the field was altered was observed in every crystal studied, although the magnitude of the jump varied from crystal to crystal. The time transients of the conductivity were observed in all crystals except Se2. The increasing transient was

Fig. 2. Conductivity transients at 300°K in the dark.

considerably slower than the decreasing one. As seen in Fig. 2, both transients proceeded almost undisturbed if the direction of the voltage was reversed. This means that the conductivity transients do not depend on the direction of the field used.

The time dependences of the conductivity during the transients are non-exponential, like the decay curves of photoconductivity in selenium. Let us define a characteristic time, t_o , as a change of conductance during the transient, $|G_{t=0} - G_{t=\infty}|$, divided by the absolute value of the initial slope of the transient, $|dG/dt|_{t=0}$. In the case of an exponential time dependence this would be the ordinary time constant. This characteristic time was essentially independent of the magnitude of field variations, although in some crystals it decreased somewhat with increasing electric field. On the other hand, these transient times depend strongly on temperature, as seen in Fig. 3. In crystal Se3

Fig. 3. Transient times vs inverse temperature in the dark.

above room temperature the decreasing transient followed equation

$$t_o \propto e^{-E/kT}, \quad E \approx 0.5 \text{ eV} \quad (2)$$

Even when decreasing temperature below room temperature the transient slowed strongly up, but the time t_o describing first part of the transient curve did not increase

much any more. A few points in Fig. 3 determined for crystal Se4 indicate roughly the same temperature dependence but with about six times larger values of $\bar{t}_o$. The characteristic times of increasing transients (after the decrease of electric field) are larger than those of decreasing transients and when decreasing temperature they increase strongly even below room temperature.

The magnitude of the conductivity jump when the electric field is changed is roughly proportional to the change in the electric field. Therefore, a quantity

$$J = \frac{\Delta \sigma}{\Delta K} = \frac{\sigma_a - \sigma_b}{K_a - K_b} \quad (3)$$

is used here in the description of the size of the transients. K_b and K_a are the respective electric fields before and after the voltage change, and σ_b and σ_a are the corresponding conductivities immediately before and after the voltage change. If σ_b does not correspond to a steady state, J depends somewhat on the history of the crystal. This effect causes some scattering in the J values, as the time required to establish a steady state before every transient is prohibitively long in a large serie of transients. In Table 3. J values of crystals Se1 to Se5 are presented. It can be seen that J is rather insensitive to field, decreasing only slightly with field in the range used. There is no strong temperature dependence in the temperature range 0 to 80 °C. Naturally J values vary from crystal to crystal, but all are of the same order of magnitude. In fact, the variation of J is smaller than the variation of the dark conductivity (Table 2). When measuring transients of different crystals as percentages of conductivity large variations were observed, but these were mainly caused by different low field conductivity values and different field ranges used (length of the crystals varied). Average J values of different crystals at room temperature in dark are

Se1:	7 nS/V
Se2:	5 nS/V
Se3:	4 nS/V
Se4:	11 nS/V
Se5:	6 nS/V.

I l l u m i n a t i o n had a strong effect on these transients. In Fig. 4 the characteristic times t_o of both voltage transients and photo-conductivity rises and decays of crystal Se1 are plotted as functions of light intensity. The intensity dependences of the different characteristic times are similar, and the order of magnitude of different t_o values corresponding to a given intensity is also the same. The characteristic times of high field transients are roughly half of the characteristic times of low field transients (recorded after the decrease of field). Correspondingly, the rise times of photoconductivity were 25 to 60 per cent of the decay times. This kind of quantitative study was carried out in crystal Se1 only, but qualitatively similar intensity dependences could also be seen in the other crystals (with the exception of Se2 exhibiting no room temperature transients).

Fig. 4. Effect of radiation intensity on the characteristic times of transients.

Low intensity light did not affect the size of the transient. On increasing the intensity the transients started to decrease and at high intensity the increasing (low field) transient usually disappeared altogether.

Under illumination at 80 °K the decreasing transients were typically somewhat larger than at 300 °K but varied strongly from crystal to crystal. Increasing transients were usually negligible, as when strongly illuminated at 300 °K.

2.4. Quenching of photoconductivity

When a small voltage was used during the illumination and a higher voltage was switched on at some time during the photoconductivity decay, the conductivity first jumped to a higher value. However, the decay rate was also increased by this higher voltage and thus when the voltage was returned to the original low value, the conductance was lower than it would have been without the high voltage pulse (Fig. 5). This quenching effect was studied in crystals Se1 to Se5 and it was found in every crystal both at 300 °K and at 80 °K. In some crystals, even »high» field 25 V/cm caused a definite quenching

Table 3. Values of $J = \Delta \sigma / \Delta K$

Crystal Se3				Other crystals				
t	K_b	K_a	J	Crystal	t	K_b	K_a	J
$^{\circ}\text{C}$	V/cm	V/cm	nS/V		$^{\circ}\text{C}$	V/cm	V/cm	nS/V
23	20	100	4.7	Se4	3	5	145	12
	100	180	4.8			145	270	(32)
	180	260	4.3			270	120	19
	260	340	4.1		23	120	48	14
	340	420	3.1			11	230	15
	420	500	3.2			230	490	11
	500	580	2.8			490	200	9
	580	500	3.2			200	11	10
	500	420	3.4			11	480	12
	420	340	3.1		48	480	8	10
	340	260	4.5			12	200	15
	260	180	4.0			200	470	10
	180	100	5.1			470	200	6
	100	20	5.2			200	8	9
	20	20	4.8					
23	100	20	4.7	Se5	23	55	87	7.4
	20	180	4.8			87	119	7.8
	180	20	4.7			119	154	6.1
	20	260	4.9			154	188	5.6
	260	20	4.4			188	224	4.8
	20	340	4.6			224	258	5.6
	340	20	4.3			258	292	4.9
	20	420	4.1			292	315	7.0
	420	20	4.0			315	285	6.0
	20	500	3.9			285	249	4.4
	500	20	3.9			249	213	4.4
	20	580	3.6			213	180	5.6
	580	20	3.4			180	147	5.4
	20	100	4.1			147	115	6.4
	100	20	3.8			115	85	6.0
20	420	4.1	85	53	6.2			
420	20	3.7	53	25	8.2			
20	100	4.7	25	4	5.9			
24	100	20	4.7	3	128	7.6		
	20	420	4.5	128	3	6.9		
	420	20	4.2	3	161	7.0		
43	20	100	4.9	161	3	6.7		
	100	20	5.3	3	196	6.3		
	20	420	4.8	196	3	5.9		
52	420	20	4.9	3	232	5.6		
	20	100	4.7	232	3	5.6		
	100	20	4.2	3	272	5.4		
	20	420	4.7	272	3	5.4		
	420	20	5.2	3	308	5.1		
80	20	100	3.4	308	3	4.9		
	100	20	2.8	3	336	4.5		
	20	420	2.8	336	3	4.6		
	420	20	3.2					
				Se1	23	15	250	6.9
						250	15	6.6
				Se2	23	18	224	4.0
						224	18	4.3
						18	745	5.3
						745	18	5.9
						18	910	6.2

Fig. 5. Quenching by field during the decay of photoconductivity.

of photoconductivity measured using a low field 10 V/cm. Again, it was the absolute magnitude but not the direction of the high field which was important.

In the long thin crystal Se5 this effect was exceptionally strong. At 300° K a pulse of magnitude 250 V/cm and duration 1.2 min reduced the low field conductivity to below the dark conductivity value (Fig. 5). At 80° K the same field caused an almost complete quenching of photoconductivity. In other crystals this kind of almost complete quenching (above 98%) needed larger fields at 80° K: about 300 V/cm in crystal Se3, about 600 V/cm in Se4, and about 800 V/cm in Se2 (fields above 200 V/cm were not used in crystal Se1 wherefore very strong quenching was not recorded). Curious bumps were found in the high voltage decay curves of Se3 at fields above 200 V/cm, as seen in Fig. 6. The shape of these bumps varied with field but also randomly. Occasionally, but not systematically, similar bumps were seen in the decay curves of other crystals at high enough fields.

A very slow decay of photoconductivity after the termination of photoexcitation is a typical phenomenon of Se single crystals at 80° K. In an earlier experiment [10] about 20 per cent of the original photo-conductivity remained a week after illumination from which it can be appreciated that almost complete quenching of the photoconductivity when a few hundred V/cm are applied to a crystal for few minutes is a drastic effect. As mentioned above, this quenching has been observed previously when pulses of 2000 V/cm or larger were used [8, 9], but the quenching effect at low fields has not been reported before.

Fig. 6. Quenching »bumps» in crystal Se3.

Fig. 7. »Delayed» high field photoconductivity decay.

An other measurement sequency also illustrates the strong dependence of the recombination rate on the electric field. A high field was used during photoexcitation, and at the time of extinguishing the light the high voltage was switched to low. When the high voltage was later switched on again, the conductivity jumped up and the decay curve of photoconductivity appeared as without interruption (Fig. 7). This »delayed decay» peak is smaller than the high field conductivity peak in quenching experiment (Fig. 5) but larger than the voltage transient peak in dark (Fig. 2). Again, this effect was strongest in crystal Se5, where at 300 °K after a 40 min decay the 250 V/cm decay curve of photoconductivity appeared almost as if without interruption. In some other crystals there was more recombination during the low field period, so that the high voltage decay peak was not so high but nevertheless distinctly higher than the dark conductivity transient. This effect was also observed in all five crystals Se1 to Se5 studied, both at 80 °K and at 300 °K.

2.5. Conductivity at 80 °K in the dark

The results of conductivity measurements at 80 °K in the dark differ essentially from results obtained at 300 °K or when illuminated at 80 °K. No ohmic region is found in steady state current vs voltage characteristics. In all crystals studied the current followed the power law $I \propto U^n$ with n varying from 3.0 to 3.6 in different crystals. As mentioned above, values of n in the range 2 to 3 have been reported in the literature. In crystals Se3, Se6, and Se7 this measurement was extended to higher fields. As seen in Fig. 8, the slope stays constant in crystal Se3 (measured up to 800 V/cm), but starts to decrease at about 500 V/cm in crystals Se6 and Se7. This decrease is irreversible, so that when returning to smaller fields the current follows a lower $I \propto U^n$ - characteristic. This behaviour could be interpreted as »quenching of electric conductivity by high electric field».

Typically there were no transients at lower fields, but at fields of 100 to 400 V/cm transients similar to those in Fig. 2 appeared. The size of these transients varied considerably from crystal to crystal (Fig. 8). In crystal Se5 transients with a magnitude of three times the steady state conductivity were recorded, while in crystal Se3, for example, the transients were weak, and an increase of field from 700 V/cm to 800 V/cm caused a transient only four percent of the steady state conductivity. Seemingly these transients are related to the irreversible curvature of the current-voltage characteristic in Fig. 8. In crystals Se6 and Se7 transients first appeared and increased strongly in the voltage range of the curvature (Fig. 8), while crystal Se3 with a straight characteristic exhibited only small transients.

In addition to varying transients, spurious polarization effects were also seen in some crystals at 80 °K in the dark. Voltage probe studies described below indicated that the electric field was not homogeneous at 80 °K in the dark in the three crystals studied. Large variations and spurious effects in the results of the conductivity measurements at 80 °K in the dark are thus to be expected.

Fig. 8. Current vs electric field, 80 °K in the dark. The current transients are described with vertical lines.

2.6. Other low field measurements

Photoconductivity rises and decays were determined in crystal Se3 with electric fields of 10 V/cm and 600 V/cm. At 300 °K the differences were small. In the higher field the rise was a little faster and the decay a little slower. At 80 °K the initial slope of the rise curve was about five times larger for the higher field than for the low field, and a »bump« similar to those in Fig. 6 appeared in the high field decay curve.

In order to check the possibility that the electric field were able to cause electron excitations, crystals Se3 and Se4 were exposed to an electric field 400 V/cm during the 5 min periods at 80 °K in the dark. Subsequently, during the warming up of each crystal a thermally stimulated current (TSC) was recorded using the low electric field. No difference was observed when comparing these TSC-curves with those measured without the high voltage exposure.

Ordinary TSC curves were recorded using various electric fields in crystal Se3. The low field TSC-curve was typical for selenium. The initial rise was proportional to $\exp(-E/kT)$ with $E \propto 0.02$ eV, a maximum was reached at about 200 °K, and after the decrease the curve started to increase again in the room temperature region. When a field of 600 V/cm was used the recombination after illumination was fast, so that the TSC-curve started at a conductivity value eight percent of that of the low field case. However, the increase of the conductivity was much faster and this curve reached a maximum 60 percent of the low field conductivity at ca. 200 °K. After a descending part steeper than in the low field case this curve also began to rise again. If after passing the maximum the heating was interrupted, the crystal cooled, and the TSC-curve was recorded again, a steeper rise and an increased temperature of max. conductivity were observed as in the low field case [6, 7].

The temperature dependence of the conductivity in the dark was determined in crystals Se3 and Se4 with the electric field as a parameter. As was mentioned in Ch. 2.2., in the room temperature region the conductivity of these crystals was proportional to the factor $\exp(-E_B/kT)$, $E_B \approx 0.14$ eV. Below room temperature the curve $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ took up a smaller slope. This low temperature slope depended strongly on the electric field, decreasing with increasing field in both crystals. As mentioned in the introduction, similar curves have been reported by S t u k e [6], showing that the conductivity becomes steadily more nonohmic with decreasing temperature.

As mentioned in the introduction, the hole concentration in Se single crystals is of order 10^{14} to 10^{15} cm⁻³ according to thermoelectric power (TEP) and Hall measurements. As the author knows of no TEP measurement in Tl-doped single crystals, a TEP was measured at room temperature in crystal Se3. The TEP obtained both in the dark and under illumination was 0.78 mV/°K. Using the conventional formula for the TEP of semiconductors one obtains a hole concentration of the order 10^{16} cm⁻³. This value is somewhat larger than the hole concentrations usually obtained with TEP-measurements in Se. Especially, it is about 200 times larger than the hole concentration obtained with a.c. Hall measurements in the Tl-doped single crystal [29].

The homogeneity of the electric field and the quality of

the contacts were studied in crystals Se3, Se4, and Se5 by using voltage probes and a high impedance voltmeter. The following statements can be made:

a. The field distribution was quite homogeneous in all three crystals above 0 °C and in illuminated crystals at lower temperatures also.

b. In some crystals, especially in crystals Se4, Se5, and Se6, it had been observed that the conductance measured in one direction was two to twenty percent larger than in the opposite direction. The bulk conductivity measured with voltage probes in Se4 and Se5 did not exhibit these differences. Therefore, the nonsymmetry of the conductance in crystals Se4, Se5, and Se6 is some kind of contact effect and in these crystals the field is weakly inhomogeneous.

c. Strong inhomogeneities of field and polarization effects occurred at 80 °K in the dark. The field was concentrated at the positive end or at both ends of the crystal, leaving a region of very small field in the middle. When crystal Se3 was cooled from room temperature to liq. nitrogen temperature using a voltage of 10 V, the voltage between the probes decreased only little, but this voltage remained when the current through the crystal was switched off. In some cases it even remained when the direction of the current was changed. Thus, in some way, the crystal was polarized. Large variations between the different measurements occurred, so that no consistent picture can be presented. The study of these phenomena at low temperature in the dark would necessitate carefully planned experiments and a new approach to the question of electric contacts to selenium.

d. During the second steep slope of the »bump»- type decay of photoconductivity (Fig. 6) the originally homogeneous electric field concentrated at the ends of the crystal. The interpretation of this effect follows in Ch. 3.3.3.

2.7. High field pulse experiments

The essential results of pulse measurements are presented in Fig. 9. At room temperature in the dark the initial current values followed a square law

$$I_{init.} = J'_H U^2, \quad J'_H = 70 \text{ nA/V}^2. \quad (4)$$

During the pulse the current decreased to a quasi-steady state value with a typical time constant of 15 μ s. These final values followed the equation

$$I_{final} = J'_H (U - 800V)^2 \quad (5)$$

Apparently there would have been a further slow decrease of current as in lower fields but this could not be recorded. Illumination increased initial and final current values about 20 percent at room temperature.

Similar behaviour but with more irregular results was obtained at 80 °K with illumination, but the J'_H value was twice that at room temperature, as seen in Fig. 9.

If the cross section of the crystal is A and its length is L we get from Eq. 4

$$\sigma_{init} = J'_H \frac{L^2}{A} K = J_H K \quad (6)$$

In crystal Se6 the cross section of the crystal was equal to the square of its length, so that in this case $J'_H = J_H$.

Eq. 6 is essentially the same as Eq. 3, because the low field conductivity can now be neglected. When comparing the high field coefficient J_H to the low field values J in Table 3, we see that at room temperature J_H is something like ten times J .

The measuring system of the pulse experiments was not good. First, the pulse system did not give exact square pulses but the voltage increased during the pulse. Secondly, the crystal was quite long (5mm), requiring large and thus impractical voltages. Thirdly, the sample was not very good. Therefore, no detailed program was carried out, except for the preliminary measurements presented in Fig. 9 which may include systematic errors. What these results show satisfactorily is the strongly non-ohmic initial current during the single pulse and, in contrast to the results of M o r t with repeated pulses [14], a complete lack of the acoustoelectric current saturation. This contradiction will be discussed in Ch. 4.

Fig. 9. Pulse experiments.

3. INTERPRETATION OF THE RESULTS

3.1. Origin of non-ohmic effects in selenium

There are many mechanisms causing non-ohmic behaviour of semiconductors. Therefore, a detailed analysis is necessary in order to distinguish between them. In the case of hexagonal Se single crystals we are able to eliminate most of the usual effects by simple reasoning:

a. High field phenomena like the Zener effect, avalanche effect, and hot carrier effects are excluded because of the small fields used and because of the small microscopic mobility of holes in Se.

b. Heating effects are excluded by the small powers used in the low field experiments and by the short pulse times used in pulse experiments.

c. Contact effects often cause non-ohmic effects in semiconductors. Bad contacts are caused by rectifying interfaces or by poorly conducting impurity layers between the semiconductor and the contact metal. Nickel or gold are normally used to obtain ohmic contacts in selenium. Voltage probes were used in order to study the homogeneity of the electric field. Above 0 °C and also at lower temperatures when illuminated most crystals had ohmic contacts and a homogeneous electric field. In crystals Se4, Se5, and Se6 the field was weakly inhomogeneous, causing side effects in measurements, e.g. different resistances in opposite directions. However, these side effects could be distinguished from the essential non-ohmic effects. Thus we can say that the essential results of this work obtained above 0 °C and at lower temperatures with illumination are not caused by any contact effect or macroscopic inhomogeneity of the electric field. At low temperatures in the dark all the crystals tested by voltage probes exhibited inhomogeneous fields. Even in this case the non-ohmic effects seem to be caused by the same mechanism as at higher temperatures (not by contact effects), but inhomogeneities enhance and distort the non-ohmic effects strongly. Obtaining reliable quantitative results at 80 °K in the dark would clearly necessitate new types of contacts and a continuous check of the homogeneity of the electric field.

d. Dipole layers created in the crystal or at the contacts cannot cause the effects observed, as reversing the voltage had no effect on the conductivity value nor on the slope of the conductivity vs time curve during the transient (except the side effects mentioned in paragraph c.). This does not exclude the possibility that some kind of dipole layers exist in Se crystals in which case the non-ohmic effects could be enhanced.

e. The non-ohmic steady state current vs voltage characteristic in Se below room temperature is often stated to arise from a space charge limited current. However, at least in crystals which are several millimetres long, the SCLC of a homogeneous crystal

would be several orders of magnitude too small. Also the dependence of current on sample thickness and the potential distribution along the sample do not correspond to SCLC [3, 5] and thus the ordinary »macroscopic» SCLC is excluded.

We conclude from the experimental results that the non-ohmic effects in Se are not caused by contact effects or by SCLC of homogeneous crystals. Also, taking into account the small hole mobility in Se, none of the usual mechanisms causing high field effects in semiconductors can create the non-ohmic effects observed in Se at small fields.

Variation of trapping parameters by the electric field causes non-ohmic effects in homogeneous CdS crystals, as observed by D u s s e l and B u b e [26]. Quenching and other effects similar to those reported here occurred in fairly small fields, from a few hundred V/cm to 3 kV/cm. It was concluded that the capture cross section for free electrons and the effective depth of the electron traps in CdS become smaller with increasing electric field. However, some results in Se can not be interpreted this way. For example, there should be no steady state conductivity changes such as observed in Se, and the TSC curves in Se are of a different type from those of CdS. Moreover, the unusual mobility and photoconductivity properties of selenium must be taken into account.

3.2. Barrier model of photoconductivity in selenium

The quantitative barrier model of photoconductivity was introduced by T u o m i for the explanation of the photoconductivity (PC) results [10]. The basic ideas in this model presented below are first the dislocation recombination mechanism and second the closed barrier network of small angle boundaries.

The dislocation recombination mechanism has been treated theoretically by R e a d [27]. According to this mechanism there are local electron states at the dislocation cores, and these act as traps for majority carriers. Thus in Se these centres are donor states, and according to PC studies they are about 0.8 eV above the valence band [10]. Let the density of these centres I be N_I and the density p_I of these centres be ionized charging the dislocations positively. To compensate this charge, free holes withdraw from the cylinder around the dislocation core, causing a space charge cylinder. The potential at an unionized dislocation centre, V_B , is roughly proportional to the density p_I ,

$$V_B = c_I p_I. \quad (7)$$

In Fig. 10 the energy bands and the hole density around the dislocation core are shown. The electrons are either thermally or optically excited to the centres I . Recombination is limited by the small hole density near the core, p_B . The density of trapped holes, p_I , is determined by the differential equation

$$-dp_I/dt = (f + g)p_I - c_r(N_I - p_I)e^{-\beta V_B}, \quad (8)$$

Fig. 10. Dislocation recombination model.

where

f is the probability for optical electron excitation to a centre I in unit time, proportional to the intensity of illumination,

g is the probability for thermal electron excitation to a centre I in unit time,

c_r is a factor proportional to the hole capture cross-section of centres I , approximately constant, and

$$\beta = e/kT.$$

In ordinary semiconductors such as germanium this dislocation recombination controls the lifetime of the free carriers. In selenium, according to thermoelectric power and Hall measurements, the density of free holes in bulk material is nearly constant. Somehow, charged dislocations act as barriers for free holes in Se causing the macroscopic d.c. mobility to decrease. Tuomi proposed that the barriers are small angle boundaries built up of parallel dislocations. The space charge cylinders overlap, and the lowest barriers for free holes are between dislocations. According to this concept the potential barrier E_B is a definite part κ of the dislocation potential energy eV_B ,

$$E_B = \kappa eV_B. \quad (9)$$

In fact, a conductivity

$$\sigma = \sigma_1 e^{-E_B/kT} \quad (10)$$

is observed in Se where E_B is about 20 percent of the potential energy eV_B . E_B depends on illumination and in illuminated crystals also on temperature, as expected from Eqs. 7, 8, and 9.

3.3. Non-ohmic effects according to the dislocation recombination model

The characteristic times of the voltage transients depend on temperature and light intensity in the same way as the PC rises and decays. It is also possible to quench out the PC during the PC decay by using a higher electric field. Therefore, same centres are involved in photoconductivity and electric field effects, and the electric field is able to increase the recombination rate of electrons excited by illumination.

The conductivity increases instantaneously when the electric field is increased, but during the transient it is normal that the increased recombination completely compensates this conductivity increase at high enough temperature. Therefore, the conductivity jump is related to the process increasing recombination rate.

For a more detailed analysis of the results, some assumptions about the recombination and mobility mechanisms must be made. It is assumed, that dislocation recombination controls the potential barriers V_B according to Eq. 8. Further it is assumed that the low field conductivity is determined by barriers V_B according to Eqs. 9 and 10, but no assumptions on mechanism behind these two equations is necessary at this stage. Fig. 11 shows the dislocation in the presence of a field. The field causes the space charge cylinder to shift as compared to the dislocation core. We define the extra electric field K_D as the voltage across the dislocation space charge divided by the cylinder diameter. This average field is also approximatively the electric field in the space charge region in excess to the equilibrium field, because the distribution of charges inside the space charge region is not changed much by the field. It is assumed that the free holes in the left hand side of Fig. 11 are in quasi-equilibrium (the equilibrium diffusion current and the net current flow in the same direction). Thus, the hole density near the dislocation core is

$$p_B = p_o e^{-\beta V_B}, \quad V_B = c_I p_I - K_D R = V_B^o - K_D R, \quad (11)$$

where V_B^o is the dislocation potential with zero electric field and V_B that with the field. Thus, Eq. 11 substitutes the Eq. 7 of low field photoconductivity model. A field increase decreases the potential V_B and increases the hole density p_B at the dislocation core, causing a faster recombination rate.

The shift of the space charge also causes an extra current to pass through the space charge region (Fig. 12). The extra current density i_D has the character of a space charge

Fig. 11. Field applied across the dislocation.

Fig. 12. The extra currents through the space charge regions. *a.* Isolated dislocation, *b.* Small angle boundary (smaller scale).

limited current and therefore increases faster than the field K_D . We make the simple assumption that this current density behaves like an ordinary SCLC increasing proportionally to the square of the voltage across the space charge cylinder, i.e. to the square of the average field K_D ,

$$i_D = c_i K_D^2, \quad (12)$$

where c_i is a constant determined by the geometry of the dislocation space charge.

The quantities determined in the experiments are the macroscopic electric field K and macroscopic electrical conductivity σ (assuming a homogeneous field on a macroscopic scale, which is correct except at 80 °K in the dark). The extra field K_D in the space charge region is at small fields approximately proportional to the macroscopic field,

$$K_D = c_K K. \quad (13)$$

In the case of an insulating cylinder in the conducting media the field inside the cylinder is twice the outer field. Thus, if the dislocations are separate, the factor c_K is about 2. If dislocations build up a closed network of small angle boundaries, one can say that a fraction P of the total volume is made up of space charge regions. In this case the field is concentrated in the high-ohmic regions and thus c_K is the inverse of P (about 10 according to the measurements of the frequency dependence of conductivity [28]).

The increase of macroscopic current density i_M caused by extra currents passing through the space charges is approximately proportional to the current density i_D ,

$$i_M = c_M i_D. \quad (14)$$

The macroscopic conductivity is according to Eqs. 9 to 14

$$\sigma(K) = \sigma(0) + \frac{i_M}{K} = \sigma_1 e^{-\kappa\beta V_B^0} + c_M c_i c_K^2 \cdot K \quad (15)$$

By combining Eqs. 11 to 14 we get expressions for the instantaneous effects of a positive or negative change ΔK in the macroscopic field,

$$\Delta V_B = -c_V \Delta K, \quad c_V = R c_K, \quad (16)$$

$$\Delta \sigma = J \Delta K, \quad J = c_M c_i c_K^2. \quad (17)$$

The experimental results of this work can now be interpreted according to this model.

3.3.1. Transients at 300 °K in the dark

According to Eq. 17 the instantaneous jump in the conductivity should be proportional to the change in field. This is approximately the case, as was seen in Table 3

where ratios $J = \Delta \sigma / \Delta K$ were tabulated. Experimental J values varied only slightly with the field range used or with temperature, in agreement with the model. Values of J varied somewhat from crystal to crystal, which is natural as dislocation structure depends on the growth method.

When the field is increased, V_B decreases according to Eq. 16 causing faster recombination according to Eq. 8, so that the density p_I and the potential V_B° begin to increase, causing a decreasing conductivity transient. Steady state is reached when V_B° has increased an amount $c_V \Delta K$ so that V_B has the same values as it had before the field was increased. Thus the increased recombination essentially compensates the extra current i_M , so that the steady state conductivity does not increase much with field. When the field is reduced, the conductivity decreases according to Eq. 17 but on the other hand the potential V_B increases an amount $c_V \Delta K$ and the recombination rate decreases. Thermal excitation g then gradually restores the steady state causing the slowly increasing conductivity transient. As the transients are caused by the change in occupation, p_I , these transients naturally proceed undisturbed when the direction of the field is reversed.

3.3.2. Transient times

In Ch. 2.3. the rises and decays of the PC as well as field measurement transients were described by characteristic times

$$t_o = \frac{|G_{t=0} - G_{t=\infty}|}{|dG/dt|_{t=0}} = \frac{|\sigma_{t=0} - \sigma_{t=\infty}|}{|d\sigma/dt|_{t=0}}. \quad (18)$$

Equations for these characteristic times can be derived from the dislocation recombination model. The variation of trapped hole density p_I caused by illumination or by an electric field is so small that it needs to be taken into account only in the exponent in Eq. 8 ($V_B = c_I p_I - K_D R$), elsewhere we can use the equilibrium density p_{I0} rather than the variable p_I . The temperature dependence of the characteristic time t_o of the PC rise and decay in the case of weak illumination $f \ll g$ is, according to Eqs. 7 to 10

$$t_o^* (\text{weak}) = \frac{1}{\beta c_I c_r (N_I - p_{I0})} \cdot e^{eV_B/kT}. \quad (19)$$

This equation has been derived in Ref. [10] using a slightly different notation*(and assuming $p_{I0} \ll N_I$). An exponential temperature dependence has also been observed experimentally with a potential value $V_B = 0.8$ V in agreement with the model. Using the same equations one may also derive the characteristic times of decay in the case of strong illumination $f \gg g$, in which case the photoconductivity $\sigma_{t=0} - \sigma_\infty$ is approximately equal to the conductivity of an illuminated crystal $\sigma_{t=0}$. One obtains

* f and g in this work are g / p_I and $c_h^I N_v$ in Ref. 10, respectively. $N_I \equiv N_d/a$, $c_r \equiv c_h p_o$, $c_I \equiv c_I / N_I$.

$$t_o^* \text{ (strong)} = \frac{1}{\kappa \beta c_I p_{I0}} \cdot \frac{1}{f}. \quad (20)$$

Thus in a strongly illuminated crystal the characteristic decay time of PC does not depend strongly on temperature but is inversely proportional to the intensity of radiation.

Using Eqs. 8 to 11 and Eqs. 16 and 17 we can now derive the equations for the characteristic times of field measurement transients caused by a field change ΔK .

$$t_o = \frac{|\Delta \sigma|}{|d\sigma/dt|_{t=0}} = \frac{J |\Delta K|}{\sigma(0) \kappa \beta c_I \left| \frac{dp_I}{dt} \right|_{t=0}}. \quad (21)$$

Assuming a steady state before field change Eq. 8 gives

$$c_r (N_I - p_I) e^{-\beta V_B(0)} = (f + g) p_{I0}. \quad (22)$$

From Eqs. 8 and 22 the derivative at $t=0$ is

$$dp_I/dt = c_r (N_I - p_I) (e^{-\beta [V_B(0) + \Delta V_B]} - e^{-\beta V_B(0)}). \quad (23)$$

Using Eqs. 21, 22, 23, and 16 for fields $\Delta K < 1/\beta c_V$ we then get

$$t_o = \frac{J}{\sigma(0) \kappa \beta^2 c_I p_{I0} c_V} \cdot \frac{1}{f + g}. \quad (24)$$

This equation is useful in the case of illuminated crystal. In the dark the potential V_B is approximately independent on temperature. Thus, using Eq. 22 we get an useful expression in the dark

$$t_o \text{ (dark)} = \frac{J}{\sigma_{t=0} \kappa \beta^2 c_I c_V c_r (N_I - p_I)} e^{eV_B/kT}. \quad (25)$$

This characteristic time corresponds to the PC time constant t_o^* under weak illumination (Eq. 19).

In Fig. 3 the characteristic times of field measurement transients in the dark were presented as functions of inverse temperature. The temperature dependence is exponential

in agreement with Eq. 25, but the energy eV_B obtained from the slopes is 0.5 eV, somewhat smaller than the value 0.8 eV obtained from PC measurements [10].

In Fig. 4 the characteristic times of field transients in illuminated crystal, as well as PC rise and decay times, were presented as functions of light intensity. According to Eqs. 20 and 24 both PC and field transient times should be inversely proportional to the light intensity ($f \gg g$). The quantitative agreement with the model is moderate.

3.3.3. Quenching and »delayed decay» of PC

If during the decay of the PC the field is increased, the conductivity first jumps according to Eq. 17. Simultaneously the recombination of photoexcited electrons becomes faster, because the dislocation potential V_B were decreased according to Eq. 16. When the field is switched back to the low value, the extra conductivity vanishes and one observes that the high field voltage period has reduced the conductivity. This is the quenching effect. On the other hand, if the high field used during illumination is removed simultaneously with the photoexcitation, then the recombination decreases to a small value and photoexcited electrons delay in the centres I . By applying a higher field at a later time one recreates nearly the same situation as at the time of the termination of the photoexcitation and thus the »delayed» decay curve of the PC appears.

As mentioned in Ch. 2.6. the electric field was quite homogeneous at 80 °K when illuminated but strongly inhomogeneous at the same temperature in the dark. This gives an explanation for the curious bumps observed often but not regularly in several crystals in quenching curves at 80 °K. At the beginning of the high field period the field is homogeneous and recombination occurs evenly in the crystal. When the conductivity decreases, the situation in the crystal becomes unstable. Let us assume that the field at the ends of the crystal is slightly larger than the average. The recombination in these areas is faster, which means that the conductivity in the ends decreases faster than in the centre. Thus the voltage concentrates more and more to the ends causing still faster recombination and a steep conductance decrease of the crystal as a whole. So the bump indicates the building up of a high field fast recombination layer across the crystal. This kind of instability depends on various factors and thus may vary from decay to decay without any obvious reason. This interpretation was checked by voltage probe measurements, and it was found that during the fast decay of the bump (Fig. 6) the field in the central area of the crystal almost vanished and the voltage concentrated to the ends of the crystal, as mentioned in Ch. 2.6.

3.3.4. Steady state current vs voltage

The electron transitions to and from centres I restore the potential V_B after the voltage has been changed, so that the steady state dislocation potential V_B does not depend on the electric field. Increased recombination compensates the extra current

through the space charge region. Therefore the steady state conductivity is essentially ohmic in the field range studied here (at high enough temperatures). However, the controlling mechanism is not straightforward. V_B is the potential at the dislocation core, but the main part of the extra current i_D does not flow through this central area of dislocation space charge. This means that although the recombination compensates the decrease of V_B it may not cause the extra current to vanish completely. Thus the exponent n in expression $I \propto U^n$ could be somewhat larger than one. On the other hand, when the recombination increases V_B^o after field increase the width of the space charge region increases (see Eq. 11). This should reduce the extra current and thus reduce the exponent n . The observed deviations of n values from the ohmic value one (depending on the type of the crystal, on temperature and illumination, and on field range used) are to be expected on the basis of these opposite effects.

3.3.5. Conductivity in the dark at low temperatures

From Eq. 8 the equilibrium thermal excitation rate g is

$$g = \frac{c_r (N_I - p_I)}{p_I} e^{-eV_B/kT} \quad (26)$$

According to [10] the potential V_B is about 0.8 V in the dark so that g decreases very rapidly with temperature. The recombination rate $c_r \exp(-\beta V_B)$ in Fig. 10 is equal to g in the dark. Thus at low temperature the recombination rate is negligible and remains very small even when the potential V_B is somewhat decreased by an electric field. Therefore one expects from the model a very low conductivity in Se at low electric fields and according to Eq. 17 a characteristic $I \propto U^2$ without any transients (the transients are too slow to be recorded). At higher fields the increase of the recombination rate might become noticeable, in which case applying a high field would cause a decreasing current transient. When subsequently returned to a low field, a reduced conductivity would appear as the negligible thermal excitation g could not restore the equilibrium. If there exist hole traps in the space around the dislocation core, the charge distribution caused by an electric field could be »frozen in» in which case after removing the external voltage source a polarization voltage should be observed in the crystal.

Experimentally, a characteristics $I \propto U^n$ with $n \approx 3$ was observed in the crystals used in this work. Typically there were no transients at lower fields but at higher fields transients appeared. The reduction of the low field conductivity caused by exposure to a higher field was observed in crystals Se6 and Se7 but not in Se3 (Fig. 8). Polarization effects were also observed in voltage probe studies. The results varied considerably from crystal to crystal, so that no consistent quantitative data about the transients can be drawn.

The voltage probe tests showed that in the low temperature experiments reported here the field was no longer homogeneous but became concentrated at one or both

ends of the crystal. In these regions the field was much higher than the average. The recombination may become appreciable in these regions of the crystal at a fairly small average field value. Thus the inhomogeneity enhances the non-ohmic effects, and the variations in the results of different crystals in Fig. 8 could be caused by various degrees of inhomogeneity. The increased value of the characteristic exponent n (three, instead of the value two expected) can also be caused by an inhomogeneous field.

It can be concluded that the experimental low temperature results of this work and of the references mentioned in the introduction do not conflict with the model. However, the results are so uncertain and limited in number that reliable facts about the non-ohmic effects in Se at low temperatures in the dark cannot be drawn. Seemingly the same processes are at work as at higher temperatures, but new types of non-ohmic behaviour may also arise in the high field layers at the ends of the crystal. New conductivity mechanisms could also become active in Se at low temperature when the ordinary »barrier limited« mobility is so small.

3.3.6. Other results

The effect of an electric field on the PC rise and decay curves in the room temperature region can easily be treated with the model. The initial conductivity is the steady state value and thus essentially independent of field. Again the variation of density p_I in Eq. 8 is taken into account only in the exponent $-\beta V_B$, where $V_B = c_I p_I - K_D R$. According to Eqs. 8 and 11 the steady state potential V_B does not depend on the field. Therefore, according to Eq. 8 the initial derivative dp_I/dt is also independent of field and thus from Eqs. 7, 9, and 10 the initial derivatives $d\sigma/dt$ of both the rise and decay of the PC are also field independent. In fact the experimental PC rises and decays at room temperature depended only rather weakly on the electric field. At 80 °K the transients depended more strongly on field, but the homogeneity of the field was changing during the PC transients as observed in voltage probe studies.

No new peaks appeared in the TSC curve when the electric field was increased. Detailed TSC measurements were not carried out in this work, but qualitatively the reported changes in the TSC curve caused by the field can be understood on the basis of the model.

4. DISCUSSION

One of the aims of this work was to determine the common non-ohmic effects in Se single crystals grown by various methods and containing different impurities. The basic phenomena, the instantaneous increase of conductivity and the increase in recombination rate, occurred in every crystal studied. It is worth while at this point to compare experimental results with those reported earlier in Se single crystals and described in Ch. 1. [1...10].

At room temperature the slope of the characteristic $\log I$ vs $\log U$ has usually been found to be unity at small fields (ohmic case) rising to higher values when the field is increased. However, values smaller than unity have also been observed. Minor deviations of this slope from unity have also been reported in this work, but no clear increase of n with increasing field. This may be a result of the smaller fields used in this work. The often reported increase in the exponent n may also be partly caused by inaccurate extrapolation. The decreasing transient after field increase (Fig. 2) is so slow that it may take hours even at room temperature to establish a steady state. Because of the non-exponential character of the curve the extrapolation easily gives too large a conductivity value.

Transients reported in earlier works vary strongly, but are usually similar to those reported here. Reasons for the variation have been elucidated and studied in this work (temperature, illumination, field range, field homogeneity). Quenching of the photoconductivity by an electric field has been reported when fields ≥ 2 kV/cm were applied. In this work quenching has been observed in all crystals at much smaller fields. In fact, according to the experimental results of this work a small quenching effect should be observed in any Se single crystal when a field of only 100 V/cm is applied at room temperature or below.

The pulse experiments of Gobrecht and Hamisch [8] are in agreement with the low field experiments reported here. The transients and quenching effect are similar to those at low fields. High transverse a.c. fields had the same effect. Assuming the dislocation recombination model it is possible that a transverse field brings holes into the space charge regions where they are available for the perpendicular d.c. current. In any case, because of the much higher fields in the pulse experiments new types of non-ohmic processes may also become possible. A hint of such a process was observed in Ref. [8]. When the high transverse field was limited to a small region of the crystal, the large conductivity path extended beyond it. Thus further measurements in the range of higher field may bring to light new non-ohmic processes.

M o r t also used high field pulses in this acoustoelectric effect studies on Se [14]. At first sight his results strongly disagree with the pulse measurements reported here

and in Ref. [8]. His crystal was ohmic up to a few kV/cm, as opposed to the present work where a quadratic I vs U characteristic was observed in Se6 (Fig. 9). However, Mort used pulses repeated 30 times per sec while in this work single pulses were used. In the case of a single pulse an initial conductivity and thus a quadratic characteristics should be observed (according to Eq. 17), while during repeated pulsing more and more recombination occurs so that more ohmic behaviour is expected. This process could, in fact, be seen when the first few of a series of pulses were recorded [8]. One further discrepancy remains, namely the acoustoelectric current saturation observed in the experiments of Mort but not in crystal Se6 of this work (Fig. 9) in the same field range. Either the effect cannot occur in an experiment using single pulses or there is some inherent difference in the crystals used. (However, in the low field and PC experiments only minor differences, except for the optical quenching properties, were observed between the crystals grown by H a r r i s o n, Se4, Se5, and Se6, and the crystal Se3 grown by K e e z e r et al. who also grew the specimens used by Mort.)

Second aim of this work was to make an unified interpretation of the non-ohmic effects in Se. This kind of interpretation was presented in Ch. 3.3. on the basis of the dislocation recombination model. This model is grossly simplified and partly phenomenological owing to the complicated barrier structure of Se and because some basic semiconductor properties of Se are not known. The approximations and assumptions made can be grouped into three categories.

1. *Different types of dislocation centres.* In the model illustrated in Figs. 10 and 11 it was assumed that all the various local electron states in all types of dislocation cores can be described by a single type of centre, I . This is a rather great simplification as, according to studies of the photoconductivity (PC) and the optical quenching of the PC in several types of Se single crystals, at least two essentially different types of imperfections are necessary in describing the PC and quenching effects [19, 9]. If the density ratio of these centres varies, large differences in the temperature dependence of the PC, in the spectral dependence of optical quenching of the PC, and in the TSC are observed. As these same centres also participate in the non-ohmic effects studied here, one might expect variations in the magnitudes of the transients, in the magnitude of field quenching etc. There are also experimental results of non-ohmic studies which can not be understood without assuming at least two types of centres. A good example is a transient experiment in the dark made on crystal Se3. A voltage of 400 V was initially applied, and a normal decreasing transient appeared. After a short time interval the voltage was decreased to 350 V, at which point the conductivity dropped and then started to increase as usually. However, it reached a maximum and then continued a slow decrease. This would be expected if the fast type of centres were mainly emptied during the 400 V period and the reverse process occurred at the lower voltage of 350 V, while the slow type of centres were emptied very little during the 400 V period and continued this process at 350 V at a somewhat lower rate. However, as this explicit appearance of more than one type of centre only occurs in exceptional measurement configurations, it is justifiable to use only one type of centre in the description of non-ohmic effects.

2. *Equations of the non-ohmic effect.* The cylindrical geometry of an isolated dislocation space charge and the more complicated geometry of a small angle boundary space charge make it difficult to calculate exactly the change in potential at the dislocation core and the extra current through the dislocation space charge. In any known geometry these quantities could be calculated numerically. In Se there are various types of dislocations more or less randomly distributed in the crystal and some of these dislocations build up small angle boundaries [10], about which little is known. Eqs. 7 to 17 thus involve two types of simplification. First, identical »average» dislocations are assumed, and secondly, the complicated and partly unknown geometry is eliminated by assuming the simplest phenomenological dependences.

3. *Macroscopic d.c. mobility in Se.* The macroscopic mobility of holes in Se is small and controlled by charged dislocations. As long as the controlling mechanism is not known it can only be treated phenomenologically as in Eqs. 9 and 10.

The results of the non-ohmic effect studies give some information about this controlling mechanism. In the concept of closed network of small angle boundaries there is a space charge layer of the order $1 \mu\text{m}$ around the boundary, and the macroscopic mobility is controlled by the lowest potential of the layers in the middle of dislocation cores [10]. The space charge regions of the barriers can take at most say ten per cent of the total volume, so that there are less than 1000 barriers per cm. The maximum voltage across the small angle boundary can be estimated to be at most a volt. Thus, in a field larger than 1000 V/cm all the barriers in series should be saturated, so that at higher fields the conductivity were determined by the microscopic mobility. This kind of very strong conductivity has not been observed in Se and strong non-ohmic effects still occur well above the field 1 kV/cm . Because of overall neutrality the thickness of the space charge layer is proportional to the density of trapped holes. Thus in strongly illuminated crystal with narrow barriers the SCLC should saturate barriers at a still lower field, which is also in conflict with the results on Se. These arguments indicate that the small angle boundary network alone cannot explain all the properties of the d.c. conductivity in selenium. Naturally the charged dislocations are also strong scattering defects, but this mechanism does not lead to the conductivity properties observed in Se. Thus the question remains open.

One may ask if it is possible to obtain large enough non-ohmic effects in the case of isolated dislocations surrounded by space charge cylinders $2R = 1 \mu\text{m}$. The SCLC through an insulating homogeneous crystal with thickness L is

$$i_{\text{SCLC}} \approx \epsilon \mu U^2 / L^3 . \quad (27)$$

In the crystal with thickness $L = 1 \mu\text{m}$, a relative dielectric constant 10, and hole mobility $\mu = 20 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ one obtains

$$\frac{i_{\text{SCLC}}}{(U/L)^2} \approx \frac{\epsilon \mu}{L} \approx 180 \text{ nS/V} . \quad (28)$$

Using this value for the maximum value of the constant c_i in Eq. 12 we can calculate the dislocation density n_D necessary for the observed J value (order of magnitude 5 nS/V). In the case of isolated dislocations c_K has the value about 2 and c_M is something like $N_D \pi R^2$. According to Eq. 17 we get

$$N_D \approx \frac{J}{c_i \pi R^2 c_K^2} \gtrsim 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-2} . \quad (29)$$

10^6 cm^{-2} corresponds to a space charge volume about one per cent of the total.

SUMMARY

The effect of an electric field on the conductivity of hexagonal selenium single crystals has been studied using crystals grown by various methods. The field range used in most measurements was 10 to 1000 V/cm. The steady state conductivity was found to be approximately ohmic in the room temperature region and also at 80 °K when illuminated, although minor deviations from ohmic behaviour occurred. Conductivity transients occurred when the field was changed, and these transients depended strongly on illumination. In every crystal studied the low field conductivity during the decay of photoconductivity could be quenched by applying a higher field, both at 300 °K and at 80 °K. In every crystal these effects began at very low fields, below 100 V/cm, but their amplitude varied from crystal to crystal. Still stronger non-ohmic effects were observed in the preliminary studies at 80 °K in the dark, e.g. a steady state characteristic $I \propto U^n$ was observed with $n \approx 3$. Some pulse measurements were also carried out.

This behaviour is not a result of contact effects or space charge limited current, and cannot be explained by the mechanisms producing non-ohmic bulk effects in normal semiconductors. The variation of trapping parameters by field, which causes non-ohmic effects in CdS, could explain most of the observed effects in hexagonal Se qualitatively, but does not account for the extraordinary photoconductivity and mobility properties.

The non-ohmic behaviour of Se is definitely a bulk effect, occurring when the contacts are ohmic and the macroscopic field is homogeneous. It is evidently caused by crystal imperfections, being observed at fields less than 100 V/cm. These imperfections seem to be native to selenium, as the same effects are observed in crystals grown by different methods and containing different impurities (Cl, Tl).

An electric field both increases the conductivity and increases the recombination rate in hexagonal Se single crystals. The connections between photoconductivity and non-ohmic effects in Se indicate, that same centres are involved in both processes. Emptying these centres causes both the photoconductivity decay and the decreasing transient after an electric field increase. The instantaneous increase of conductivity after a field rise is also connected with the recombination mechanism, because the conductivity increase is gradually compensated by increased recombination. Room temperature transients, field quenching phenomena and other experimental results in the room temperature region and below for illuminated crystals can be interpreted on the basis of the dislocation recombination model earlier applied to the photoconductivity results in Se. The same mechanism is seemingly effective at low temperatures in the dark or when fields of several kV/cm are applied, but more investigations are needed to investigate other possible non-ohmic mechanisms under these conditions.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. H e n k e l s: Electrical properties of Se: I. Single crystals, J. Appl. Phys. 1951 p. 916.
- [2] K. P l e s s n e r: Conductivity, Hall effect and thermoelectric power of Se single crystals. Proc. Phys. Soc. B 64 (1951) p. 671.
- [3] M. P o l k e, J. S t u k e, E. V i n a r i c k y: Raumladungsbegrenzte Ströme in hexagonalen Se-Kristallen, Phys. Stat. Sol. 3 (1963) p. 1885.
- [4] M. B a k i r o v and N. D z h a l i l o v: Space-charge limited currents in Se single crystals, Sov. Phys. Sol. St. 8 (1966) p. 244. Translated from Fiz. Tverd. Tela 8 (1966) p. 293.
- [5] R. G r a e f f e and J. H e l e s k i v i: Measurements of space charge limited currents in hexagonal selenium single crystals. Helsinki 1966. [Acta Polytechn. Scand. Physics incl. Nucleonics 42].
- [6] J. S t u k e: Über den elektrischen Leitungsmechanismus von hexagonalen Selen-Einkristallen, Phys. Stat. Sol. 6 (1964) p. 441 and Recent Advances in Selenium Physics. Pergamon Press Ltd., 1965 p. 48.
- [7] S. H e m i l ä and T. T u o m i: Investigations of the photoconductivity in hexagonal selenium single crystals. Helsinki 1966 [Ann. Acad. Sci. Fenn. A VI 199]
- [8] H. G o b r e c h t und H. H a m i s c h: Zur Feldstärkeabhängigkeit der elektrischen Leitfähigkeit von Seleneinkristallen, Z. Phys. 148 (1957) p. 218.
- [9] W. F u h s and J. S t u k e: Hopping recombination in trigonal selenium single crystal, Phys. Stat. Sol. 27 (1968) p. 171.
- [10] T. T u o m i: Photoconductivity of hexagonal selenium single crystals. Helsinki 1968. [Acta Polytechn. Scand. Physics incl. Nucleonics 56].
- [11] J. H e l e s k i v i, T. S t u b b, and T. S u n t o l a: Direct-current measurement of the Hall effect in trigonal selenium single crystal, J. Appl. Phys. 40 (1969) p. 2923.
- [12] J. S t u k e and K. W e n d t: Phonon-drag in hexagonal Se crystals, Phys. Stat. Sol. 8 (1965) p. 533.
- [13] G. A b d u l l a y e v, N. D z h a l i l o v, and G. A l i y e v: On the heat conductivity and thermoelectromotive force of hexagonal Se single crystals, Phys. Lett. 23 (1966) p. 217.
- [14] J. M o r t: Acoustoelectric current saturation in trigonal selenium, Phys. Rev. Lett. 18 (1967) p. 540.
- [15] H. M e l l and J. S t u k e: Magnetoconductivity of hexagonal selenium single crystals, Phys. Lett. 20 (1966) p. 222.

- [16] R. L i l j a and T. S t u b b : A study on the dielectric constant and resistivity of amorphous, polycrystalline and monocrystalline selenium at 24 GHz. Helsinki 1964 [Acta Polytechn. Scand. Physics incl. Nucleonics 28].
- [17] J. M o r t : Transient photoconductivity in trigonal selenium single crystals, J. Appl. Phys. 39 (1968) p. 3543.
- [18] G. L u c o v s k y, R. K e e z e r, and E. B u r s t e i n : Infra-red lattice bands of trigonal tellurium and selenium, Solid State Comm. 5 (1967) p. 439.
- [19] S. H e m i l ä : Optical quenching of photoconductivity in hexagonal selenium single crystals, Helsinki 1969 [Ann. Acad. Sci. Fenn. A VI 323].
- [20] P. K h o d o s e v i c h and B. K o l o m i e t s : Photoconductivity of selenium at low temperatures, Sov. Phys. Solid St. 6 (1964) p. 1034. Translated from Fiz. Tverd. Tela 6 (1964) p. 1325.
- [21] T. S t u b b and J. T a l l q v i s t : Investigation of monocrystalline selenium grown from liquid phase. Helsinki 1963. Radio and Electronics Lab. Report S 3, Techn. Univ. of Helsinki.
- [22] T. S t u b b , Recent advances in selenium physics, Pergamon Press Ltd, 1965 p. 53.
- [23] F. E c k a r t , Recent advances in selenium physics, Pergamon Press Ltd, 1965 p. 83.
- [24] R. K e e z e r, C. W o o d, and J. M o o d y : Crystal growth, Proc. Int. Conf. on Crystal Growth, Boston 1966. Pergamon Press Ltd, 1967, p. 119.
- [25] D. H a r r i s o n , Recent advances in selenium physics, Pergamon Press Ltd, 1965, p. 67.
- [26] G. D u s s e l and R. B u b e : Electric field effects in trapping processes, J. Appl. Phys. 37 (1966) p. 2797.
- [27] W. R e a d, Jr: Theory of dislocations in germanium, Phil. Mag. 45 (1954) p. 775.
- [28] J. H e l e s k i v i, T. S a l o, and T. S t u b b ; The conductivity mechanism in monocrystalline selenium. Helsinki 1969. [Valtion teknillinen tutkimuslaitos. Julkaisu 147].
- [29] M. A m i t a y : Hall effect studies of temperature anomalies of carrier densities in trigonal selenium, Bull. Am. Phys. Soc. II 14 (1969) p. 737.